

DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING UNDER STATIC CONDITIONS OF A

B-Al LOAD TRANSFER ELEMENT ⁺⁾

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High strength aircraft structures can be manufactured from Boron fibre reinforced Aluminium (B-Al). B-Al structural components, including a load transfer element, have been manufactured and tested at MBB.

The load transfer element consists of fan shaped B-Al corrugated webs joined to B-Al cover sheets of varying thickness. The results is, force applied at a point can be distributed over a large area. Furthermore, by using appropriate cross and angle ply orientations one can use B-Al's inherently excellent strength and stiffness to the full. The stress analysis for this component was obtained by the F.E. method as well as other computer programmes developed at MBB. Special attention was directed to calculating the B-Al web dimensions and their fixture to the cover sheets. The finished element incorporates two basic substructures - the corrugated webs are obtained by braze bonding tapes; the laminated cover sheets are made by using a "mask" in order to obtain the required varying cross sections during the braze bonding process (MBB process). A low pressure autoclave was used throughout. Machining tapes and diamond cutting tools and EDM will be discussed as well as the assembly of the subcomponents. The load distribution, web buckling strength and joint shear strength of this load transfer element was determined by static fracture tests. This strength/weight optimized structural element is intended for the use in aircraft structures.

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Introduction

This study takes up the much discussed problem of a load transfer configuration being suitable for fiber composite material. Conventionally designed mountings of hybrid construction will get a component of comparison by this new design, whereat this new component will aid in showing the way toward new systems of load transfer. The new material and the appertaining new structure geometry are two basic elements considered as decisive for this experimental approach.

B-Al Composite as new material

Boron reinforced aluminium is outstanding in the field of fiber composite materials for its high specific strength and stiffness. Utilisation of this material is thus suitable for primary structures of light weight construction and also hybrid configurations for given pathes of force propagation. Complementary to these qualities are good properties in the fields of fatigue strength, temperature resistance, crack stopping, armour properties, safeguard against lightening strokes, inflammability, good thermal conductivity, metallic behaviour in joint systems such as brazing, spot welding and connexion by bolts. These properties have been found and confirmed in many specimens and components loaded in one or more axis directions. Measured strength values for different laminate types are as depicted in Fig. 1. These laminate types are manufactured by using the braze-bonding procedure. The materials to start with, were tapes as furnished by CMC (in former times Hamilton Standard), which are composed of the Al-foil 713, 5.7 mil borsic fibres and a plasma sprayed layer of Al 6061.

The material characteristics and the experience of MBB as elaborated in the treatment of B-Al in a braze-bonding procedure permit the manufacture of specimens and components of high quality (Fig. 2). The generally high level of technology at MBB contributes also to this accomplishment and permits to study these specimens and components under complex conditions. The results thus found were confronted and checked with theoretically derived properties of the material and taken into account in further studies.

Design of a Load Transfer Element

Considerations about structural geometry are aimed at solving the problem of introducing a force which attacks at a point into areal structures. Efforts are directed toward the manufacture of a load transfer element of boron reinforced aluminium which effects a

general improvement in performance and also additional safety against total failure of a vitally important structural part at partial destruction of the latter. Simultaneously, better fatigue properties are achieved even, under aggravated thermal conditions (Fig. 3).

Areal light weight components are frequently manufactured in sandwich construction. Introduction of forces into those components, however, is not without problems, since sandwich constructions present only then enough strength against the initiation of forces, if large areas can be utilised for force distribution. A solution consists in designing a mounting in such a way that webs will be arranged in fan shape and the cover sheets on top of it designed in a stepped fashion. The sheets in step configuration may have symmetrical as well as asymmetrical contours or setup respectively. Shaping and design will be suited to the distribution of acting forces. In conformity with a further development of the construction of webs, flanges can be provided on the edges; there is also a decreasing corrugation height or a longitudinal expansion of corrugation. The webs may be of fiber reinforced composite material or may be constructed from a single or as a combination of different kinds of material. Concentrating webs in a block in the force articulation point leads to a suitable compilation of material which in turn permits the installation of a linkage member for force application either in form of a bushing or of a flange.

Connections of the leave shaped cover sheets of step configuration will be made to fan shaped webs by brazing or bolt type connections. Fan shaped corrugated webs and cover sheets are integrated into the individual components of the main structure, in order to obtain a positive coupling between the force initiating element and the major, component to be connected. The conception of the entire load transfer element was affected by aspects of production and economy. For optimum exploitation especially the size of the load transfer element is intended to be designed much larger in aircraft components.

Leave-like Cover Sheets of Step Configuration

The leave-like shape of the cover sheets results on the one hand from the fundamental conception of the force initiating element and on the other hand from weight considerations. This is due to the fact, that the continuously decreasing load is transferred from the fan shaped webs with the individual protruding "tongues" into the main component via web flanges, i.e. in this case via cover sheets. The rounding-off of corners and the conical shape of tongues should not only reduce notch effects, but also prevent discontinuities of stress and stiffness within this context. For this cover sheet lengths of steps and "tongues" are matched to the

load distribution with respect to the force articulation point. The spread of 45° to the right and to the left hand side ensures, that even the extreme outer tongues shall be utilized for transfer of forces. The progressive displacement of individual webs and thus of the tongues of the cover sheets, too, results in a tendency of symmetrical orientation of forces toward the center of the component. A multilayer configuration was chosen, in order to obtain high strength and stiffness, both in web- and tongue direction. This crossply configuration, therefore, is selected to provide the condition required in particular for the given layer thickness and step number. In the force articulation point or more precise: in the first step of the cover sheet this yields a multilayer type of the following configuration: 20 % 0° ; 80 % $+45^\circ$ and the same setup once more for the remaining cover sheet.

Corrugated Webs in Fan Shape Configuration

The individual web basically is composed of the corrugated part (8 mm radius and 10 mm graduation) and the shaft part, which may form either a straight line or an obtuse angle with the corrugated part. All webs have a 15 mm \varnothing H7 hole receiving a steel bushing and shall be adapted in height to the steps of the cover sheets. Corresponding to the shear - and compression load a crossply arrangement of $45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ$ was chosen which possesses good bearing characteristics besides good buckling and shear strength. The shaft lengths of the symmetrically arranged webs are chosen in such a way that the combination of shafts also assume wedge shape at the projection beyond the force articulation point.

Mutually Combined Effects of the Entire Construction

A steel bushing of 15 mm \varnothing g6 (inner diameter 12 mm \varnothing H7) shall be inserted into the webs. The steel bushing can be loaded only in radial direction. Besides the concentration of webs, load transfer is achieved also via two additional mountings, in order to aid the load transfer from the force initiation point into webs and the stiff and rigid cover sheets. The mountings are made of the Al-alloy 3.3214.7 and are equipped with a 15 mm \varnothing H7 hole designed also for the insertion of the steel bushing. The flanges of the mountings are designed to reduce stiffness transitions. At the same time the shear initiation face of the entire mounting is thus augmented and the flange adapted to the basic conception of the component. The load transfer element is then installed (Fig. 4) into a sandwich plate (perceived as main structure) whereby a shear resistant connection is established between individual webs and the core of the honeycomb structure. Due to the possibility of individually different layouts, the described individual components of the load transfer element are designed to permit the adapting of the whole construction to very different conditions.

It is possible to influence the force distribution in the main structure not only by altering the corrugation characteristics of the webs, but also by choice of the type of cross-ply. Due to its shear strength, the B-Al material appears to be particularly suited to an application of this basic design to large size constructions, id est to construction heights and to high forces to be introduced. Almost every desired force distribution in the structure can be achieved by a suitable choice of the spread angle and of web lengths. When using the described design principles, a mutual coordination in the design of the individual components respecting the external forces is possible and can be effected in a rather simple way in order to achieve the goal of optimum structural design.

Static Calculation of the Load Transfer Element

For the load test, the load transfer element was installed into a cantilever beam designed as a sandwich construction. The load transfer element is stressed in the load introduction point by a single point force. The load distribution in the cover sheets must be determined to allow the efficiency of the B-Al-component to be concluded. Since the force is exerted normal to the cantilever beam, only bending enters into the static calculation of the load case (Fig. 5).

The accuracy required in determination of the load distribution and the utilisation of anisotropic materials necessitated a FEM-calculation which was performed by means of the program NASTRAN, Version 23 A. The idealisation of the component was carried out according to its structural design. In particular location and kind of force introduction was taken into account. The structural subdivision was chosen in such a manner as to permit a good representation of the hybrid structure configuration in the area of the load transfer element. The shape of the B-Al corrugated webs was idealized by straight B-Al webs in order to limit the number of necessary structural elements. The shear behaviour of the corrugated webs in web direction was taken into account in the calculation by selecting adequate dimensions of the elements used. The honeycomb structure parts were replaced by a web system consisting of isotropic material, since the computer program NASTRAN does not have 8 node-core elements for the idealisation of honeycomb cores. The stiffness values and the thickness dimensions were calculated for each web element according to the honeycomb core substituted by the web and used in the FEM-calculation. For reason of symmetry only the left hand side of the component was considered in calculation. The support of the cantilever beam and its symmetry were taken into account among the inputs by locking some degrees of freedom of the points concerned. The input comprizes the geometrical data of the

nodal points, the different elements, data of the used materials and the external loads or the external deformations. The following elements were used: the CQDMEM-quadrilateral element, the CTRMEM-triangle element. With suitable material cards, these elements are appropriate for both isotropic and anisotropic materials. The idealisation covers 6 different material combinations. The stiffness matrices of the 5 anisotropic materials as resulting from the hybrid structural design of the component were determined by the computer program B-AL-POLAR with adaption of these matrix calculations to the results of tests on cover sheets and corrugated webs. The stiffness matrices could be used as input data for NASTRAN after transformation into the orthotropic axis of the materials. The materials were read-in by the following cards: MAT1-material card for isotropic material, MAT2-material card for anisotropic material. The output of the NASTRAN computer program contains the deformations of each single node for every load case; stresses in the element are printed for every element. Furthermore the major stresses and their directions are stated for elements of isotropic material. The possibility of stress plotting as provided by NASTRAN was used to simplify evaluation of stresses. These representations of major stresses display lines of equal stress values. The stress level of each line was fed-in as input in such a way as to permit a representative picture of its distribution. The mutual normal distance of the individual lines is a measure of the stress increase in the parts of the structure. These stress distributions were calculated by applying an external deformation of $z = 5 \text{ mm}$ corresponding to an external load of $P = 7265,0 \text{ (N)}$. The thus found stress ratios and the fracture shear stress of the bonding joint as determined by test $\tau_m = 36,0 \text{ N/mm}^2$ permit the calculation of the fracture load $P = 9654,0 \text{ N}$, at which bonding failure will occur between corrugated webs and cover sheet.

Manufacture of the Load Transfer Element

Manufacture of the Stepped Cover Sheets

Tailoring of the B-Al-tapes (material thickness $\approx 0,25 \text{ mm}$, dull surface) was carried out with a high performance CO_2 -gas laser with photo-electrically controlled guide path of the MESSER-GRIESHEIM Company. Laser power was 200 watts. The cutting head with capacitive height scanning achieved a feed of 3 m/min at a cut joint width of $0,3 \text{ mm}$ and a dimensional accuracy per cut of $\pm 0,2 \text{ mm}$. Nitrogen was used as inert gas. Metallurgical tests of the cutting faces displayed no essential change of the cut material. All parts were satisfactorily cut as regards required cut shape, cut quality, cleanliness and reproduceability (a drawing template was used). The further treatment of cut tapes to Boron

reinforced Al-sheets was performed by means of the braze-bonding process (Fig. 6) at a temperature of 595° centigrade, a pressure of 880 Kilopascal and an exposure time of 15 minutes in a conventional autoclave. The steel envelope between the heating mats was evacuated to 6,6 Pa. The step shape was made more accurate by using a steel die as mask. The cover sheet was then given its final contour by spark erosion treatment ("EDM"). To this end the Agietron 25L spark erosion machine was used; it was equipped with an S.E. copper anode. The erosion of the external contour was made at 50 Volts - 5 Amp., erosion oil JM-E constituting the dielectric.

Manufacture of the Corrugated Webs

The forming capability of the tapes is not depending on the Al-matrix but, on borsic fibers. In individual tests at ambient (room) temperature it was demonstrated that a bend radius of 8 mm at an angle of aperture of 120° is permissible. Tests in anticipation of the manufacturing procedure have shown that no creep deformation does occur, since the boron fibers of the tapes display only minimum elongation. This means, that complex shapings such as those of the corrugated webs cannot be made compatible with the braze-bonding process (Fig. 7). The setup for manufacture of the corrugated webs, thus, consists of a preforming tool, a forming tool and the evacuated steel envelope used in the braze-bonding process. At the beginning of corrugated web manufacture, wave shape after wave shape is impressed into the contour via preforming tool, whereat the tapes laying one above the other can adapt themselves to the changes encountered in length by corresponding shifts. A pressure of 880 Kilopascal is exerted at a temperature of 595° centigrade; the thus pretreated braze-bonding package is exposed to the full isostatic pressure enabling the braze-bonding during an exposure time of 15 minutes. At the above parameters internal stresses due to the cold forming process are relieved. According to the above said, forming is achieved by the isostatic pressure independent of the preforming tools (press pads). The accuracy of the shape corresponds to the degree of tape shrinkage and the tolerances between preforming tool and contour shaping tool. Fidelity of shape in our case is obtained within + 0.2 mm at a tolerance in thickness of ± 0.05 mm. The webs are subsequently treated by a diamond plated disque and drilled either via spark erosion or diamond dusted hollow drill.

Assembly

The individual components assembled and adjusted in a jig as in bonding of conventional materials (Fig. 8); pretreatment of B-Al-parts, however is changed. After low-energy sand blasting, the surface will be degreased by perchlorethylene at 80° C for a period of 15 minutes. Next in line is an alkaline cleaning at 60° C for

20 minutes. Prior to and after the subsequent pickling for 5 minutes at 60° C, rinsing is performed for 3 minutes at room temperature. The preparation for bonding is terminated by drying for 15 minutes in an oven. The fan shaped configuration of the corrugated webs is bonded by means of Epon 934 (Hysol Division) at room temperature; all other bonding processes are carried out by means of AF 3002 at 175° C, one hour in the evacuated envelope at an additional outside pressure of 300 Kilopascal. All components of the main structure like the honeycomb core, cover sheets and fan are bonded with FM 1000 (Bloomingdale) in the same work cycle. Taking the temperature resistance of B-Al into account, use of soldering shall be provided for further experiments, to become independent of the shear strength limit $\tau_m = 30 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the joint system, as caused by bonding, and to be independent also of the temperature limit of 150° C. The bonding quality of the entire construction is thus augmented and homogenized. B-Al and Al or Ti have already been successfully brazed as far as small components are concerned.

Testing and Monitoring

Manufacturing Control of the integrated test support beam

Prior to the static fracture test of the integrated test support beam, the following critical parameters were monitored or tested respectively, in accordance with the measurement and test system developed as depicted in Fig. 9. During the entire bonding process in the autoclave it was possible to correctly maintain the prescribed time histories of temperature, pressure and vacuum. Prior to curing at room temperature heating to 177° C took place; this temperature was maintained for 70 minutes with a fluctuation of $\pm 1^\circ \text{ C}$ at a pressure of 275 kPa. The bonding specimens as tested for comparison within the same charge yielded a mean shear strength of $\tau = 47.3 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (FM 1000). Subsequent X-ray exposures displayed no defects and confirmed the correct position of the load transfer element within the test component carrier (Fig. 10). The splicing of the corrugated webs in the honeycomb core is clearly visible. Furthermore, the leave-like B-Al cover sheet can be seen as well as the steel bushing installed in the two Al-flanges and in the concentrated corrugated webs. The homogenous spacing of the corrugated webs and their congruent axis positions with regard to that of the cover sheet were clearly recognizable, too. The Fokker-Bond-test prescribed for the specified measuring points could not be performed, since the cover sheets were too thick. Instead of the Fokker-Bond tests all measuring points concerning Al-sheet-to-honeycomb connections were tested by ultrasound inspection and found to be in order. On visual inspection - which, of course, covered only the stepped cover sheets and the

lateral faces - defects could not be detected. The dimensional check (thickness check) yielded a deviation in thickness of ± 0.12 mm as maximum as far as the thick area of cover sheets was concerned. However, in the thin area of cover sheets and especially above the flanges in the area of web concentration a deviation in thickness of ± 0.2 mm was found. The deviation is unilateral, meaning that the cover sheet in the bonding jig is plane, whereas the different tolerances resulting from the individual parts are accumulated toward the upper surface.

Static strength test of individual components

Investigations on individual components are required, in order to be able to evaluate the static behavior of this load transfer component. The essential points in this context are the elastic behavior of the two fan shaped cover sheets, the connection between corrugated webs and cover sheets and also the compression and shear behavior of the corrugated webs themselves (Fig. 11). A separate sheet manufactured from the same charge and of identical setup was cut into test coupons and used for study of the cover sheets. In this figure stiffness values and fracture stresses are shown. Stiffness values in all directions of the entire composite structure can thus be calculated using the already determined values of the elastic quantities together with the available corresponding computer programs. A shear tensile test was performed on a corrugated web especially fabricated for this purpose in order to study the shear strength of the connection between corrugated webs and cover sheets. The corrugated web laying in the symmetry axis was used. This web had the defined crossply and was bonded to two Al-plate flanges by the bonding process as prescribed for B-Al-parts. The initial introduction of the tensile loads was made via the flanges using a stepwise increase of loads. The relative shifts of the flanges were measured after each application of a load step. The same figure also depicts the measured deformation of the bonding material on one side of the corrugated B-Al-web neglecting the deformation of the web itself. The shear fracture stress was averaged over the length of the bonding line and determined as $\tau = 39.6 \text{ N/mm}^2$. This comparatively high value can be explained by the existing fillet joint as well as by the corrugation shape of the web. Some pieces of the dimensions 41×39 mm were used to study the compression strength of the corrugated B-Al webs. The specimens were exposed to a compression stress between two parallel plates of the tensile-test machine; fracture load was recorded. Due to the wave shape of the specimens which increases stiffness in load direction, all specimens experienced pure upsetting fractures. During all these tests instability of specimens was in no case the cause of the failure. The compression fracture strength determined as arithmetic mean of all specimens is $\sigma_c = 277.6 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The test with pure shear load eventually shall be repeated, since neither technological nor

experimental presuppositions were met to test the corrugated webs. For the time being it was found that for the given design of the load transfer element, the webs are not subject to critical shear stresses. For this reason the shear stress for the webs was determined by using the observed crossply characteristics and the theoretical fundamentals involved. The tests on individual components as described in here show, that a design of the load transfer element of the indicated configuration appears to be feasible.

Fracture Test of the Load Transfer Element

For the test, the test support is bolted to two steel plates for attachment; a slanting at the lower frontal end permits a deformation of the entire test specimen in such a way that excessive stress peaks cannot occur at the location of compression at the clamping areas (Fig. 12). Furthermore, a hole in horizontal direction through the honeycomb core was provided allowing to plug a fastening bolt through the steel bushing of the load transfer element and into the fork of the cylinder. Dial gages, strain gages, tear-wires and a photo elasticity field were installed on the cover sheets, in order to measure the total behavior of the skins of the test support. The defined test support which contains the load transfer element is loaded during the test, until failure becomes apparent on one of the components either via recorded data or by continuous optical control. The load will be applied stepwise, and all measured data are interrogated and checked after each load increase. The load steps are $\Delta P = 1000$ N at the beginning of the test and are lowered to $\Delta P = 250$ N when approaching the theoretically computed fracture load of the component. In this way it is possible to obtain results which can be evaluated and almost reach actual fracture load.

The force as given by the chosen load spectrum was exerted by a hydraulic cylinder ($P = 50\ 000$ N) and directly introduced into the steel bushing of the load transfer element. The test component was designed as cantilever beam and fixed by two steel brackets (Fig. 12). The cylinder attachments take care of a torque free load transfer by intercoupling of two ball bushings. A load cell (measurement range $50\ 000$ N) is installed between the load transfer flange and the piston rod. Pressure generation and adjustment of individual load steps was carried out by manually controlled devices. The part of the test system which constitutes the measuring section permitted the measurement of the forces (via load cell), of the deformations (via dial gages with an accuracy of indication $1/100$ mm), of strains (via strain gages) and the indication of fractures via tearing wires (24 V/ 30 mA). Signals originating in the strain gages were led via measurement amplifier,

strain gage selector devices and a A/D (analog/digital) converter as well as code converter and recorded either on teletype tape and paper print. The data carrier of the teletype permits processing of the information (i.e. strains) by a computer program developed to this purpose.

Execution of test

The test was carried out in compliance with former experiences and specified parameters. The loads as applied were checked via digital indicating instruments and maintained with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$ they were kept constant during a measurement. Each measurement can thus, be allotted to the corresponding load step facilitating thereby evaluation of the data obtained. Dial gage U1 was installed for determination of the symmetry of the test setup which allowed continuous control of the test setup.

Observations and evaluation

During the entire test, dial gauges indicated a uniform symmetrical bending deformation of the integrated test component (Fig. 13). Dial gauges U1 and U3 displayed a discrepancy of only ± 0.015 mm for a maximum measured value of 10.265 mm. The continuous observation of the strain gage readings of DMS 1 through 5 confirmed the high accuracy of the component and its test jig. Strain gauges DSM 1 and 2 differed in indication by $\pm 4,2\%$. Strain gauges DSM 4 and 3 measured nearly equal amounts for tensile and compression stress loads in the cover sheets. The steps in the photo elasticity field corresponding to those in the cover sheets complicated the tracking of strain changes. Only at high load levels, observations yielded recognisable strain changes in the load introduction area. The test component itself displayed no external changes until rupture, that is, such changes were found neither in the area of clamping nor in the area of clamping nor in the region of force introduction. After applying a load of 17 000 Newton, a subsequent load increase resulted in a sudden rupture of the integrated test support beam in the area of load introduction.

The measured values as depicted on the 5 dial gauges indicate the expected linear relationship until a point closely beneath the rupture load. The measured values came close to the ones having been expected on grounds of the dimensional design and the stress analysis. When comparing values measured at U2 with those of U1 and U3, the displacement measurements are disclosing the influence of the force introduction element by displaying a relatively large difference of 4.8 mm. The continuous curves of the measurements are an indication of a correct manufacture of the test specimen. By the same token, the quality of the test specimen's clamping has

been demonstrated and the suitability of the entire test setup as well.

The stresses measured in the upper cover sheet of the integrated test specimen support beam are represented as principle stresses for the final load level. Since the amounts of the stress quantities are depending on the thickness of the cover sheets, these stress amounts are not the important parameters but rather the angular positions of the stress vectors in relation to each other. The vector field shows the increase of the stress amounts in correspondence with the curve of the bending moments; it displays also the increasing conformity of the angular orientation of the stress vectors with increasing distance from the force initiation point. The maximum deviation of the principal stress σ_1 from the symmetry axis is only 2° at the test points of row III, while at those of row I the angular deviation maximum is 19° . At the same time, a decrease of the spread of measured stress amounts in the individual rows should be noticed, decreasing from 41 % in row I to 15 % in row III and going down to merely $\pm 1,4$ % at the test points, that is: strain gauges - DMS 4 and 5. The vector field depicted shows clearly the expected stress distribution and the efficiency of the studied load transfer element.

It can be precisely recognised that the stress distribution is getting more complex the closer it comes to the load initiation point leading finally to component failure in this area. The suddenness of the rupture process allows an analysis only in conjunction with theoretical considerations. The initiation of the rupture process must have been caused by a failure of some parts of the bonding layer between the upper cover sheet and the corrugated webs. The appertaining change of the load distribution resulted in a separation of the lower cover sheet from the honeycomb core which together with a simultaneous increase in bending load on the corrugated webs led to a complete ruptural damage of the fan and thus to total component failure. In accordance with expectations the adhesive constituting the joint was the weakest member of the load transfer chain. An optimum exploitation of the load transfer element can be achieved when utilizing high quality joints as may be concluded from the favourable results with respect to the measured load distribution.

Conclusion

A load transfer element of a composite material structure configuration was designed and calculated, manufactured and tested with special view to the behaviour of boron reinforced aluminium. For the field of application of this composite material a compo-

ment was thus achieved being comparable to mountings made of conventional materials. The suitability of the used development procedure was confirmed when testing the load transfer element.

- The utilised design principle has proven outstandingly efficient in obtaining an areal stress distribution.
- Formed boron reinforced aluminium parts can be manufactured using the braze-bonding process.
- The chosen test conception has demonstrated its suitability for solving the problem; the measurement results satisfy theoretical expectations.
- With the utilised stress system the mechanical behaviour of similar components can now be more precisely determined by the evaluation of these test results.

For aircraft structures a larger design of this load transfer element appears to be promising.

Acknowledgment

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References

All additionally used references either from Germany or abroad are documented in the following MBB-reports:

MBB-UFE-793-71

MBB-UFE-1053

MBB-UFE-794-71

MBB-UFE-1147

MBB-UFE-903-72

MBB-UFE-1095

Grundmaterial - Tapes von Hamilton Standard (B-SiC Faser, 6061/713, $V_f = 50$ o/o)
 Verarbeitung durch Braze-Bonding-Prozeß (595°C, 880 kPa, 15 min)

Statische Kennwerte bei RT	
100 o/o, 0°Lagen $V_f = 50$ o/o	
σ_{11}	= 1060 N/mm ²
σ_{22}	= 130 N/mm ²
τ_{12}	= 90 N/mm ²
E_{11}	= 210 kN/mm ²
E_{22}	= 101 kN/mm ²
G_{12}	= 46 kN/mm ²

$$\rho = 2,7 \text{ g/cm}^3$$

Statische Kennwerte bei RT	
20 o/o, 0°Lagen $V_f = 50$ o/o	
80 o/o, +45°Lagen	
σ_{11}	= 330 N/mm ²
σ_{22}	= 250 N/mm ²
τ_{12}	= 150 N/mm ²
E_{11}	= 152 kN/mm ²
E_{22}	= 130 kN/mm ²
G_{12}	= 75 kN/mm ²

Statische Kennwerte bei Temperatur (T)	
100 o/o, 0°Lagen $V_f = 50$ o/o	
T = 150°C	T = 350°C
$\sigma_{11} = 1030 \text{ N/mm}^2$	$\sigma_{11} = 1000 \text{ N/mm}^2$
$\sigma_{22} = 95 \text{ N/mm}^2$	$\sigma_{22} = 90 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Lochleibungskennwerte bei RT	
20 o/o, 0°Lagen $V_f = 50$ o/o	
80 o/o, +45°Lagen	
e/D = 2,5	e/D = 2
$F_{bry} = 720 \text{ N/mm}^2$	$F_{bry} = 652 \text{ N/mm}^2$
$F_{bru} = 802 \text{ N/mm}^2$	$F_{bru} = 710 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Schwingfestigkeitswerte $N_{Bruch} = 10^6$ (LS) bei RT	
100 o/o, 0°Lagen : $V_f = 50$ o/o ; ungekerbte Probe	
R = 0,1	$\sigma_{011} = 1000 \text{ N/mm}^2$

MBB

Fig. 1 Mechanical characteristics of boron reinforced aluminum (manufactured by the braze-bonding process)

Fig.2 Manufactured and tested specimens and components of boron reinforced aluminum

MBB

1008

Fig. 3 Basic scheme of the load transfer element of boron reinforced aluminum

6001

Fig. 4 Test support with built-in load transfer element of boron reinforced aluminum

Fig. 5 Static dimensioning procedure and calculated stress distributions

Fig.6 Braze-bonding process for boron reinforced aluminum (masking procedure for cover sheets)

Fig.7 Braze-bonding procedure for boron reinforced aluminum (with preforming of the corrugated webs)

Fig.8 Assembly of the load transfer element and the test support (test jig)

Fig.10 X-ray photograph of the load transfer element in its carrier structure

Schubbruchspannung
in der Verklebung
 $\tau_m = 39,6 \text{ N/mm}^2$

MBB

Druckbruchspannung
der Wellstege
 $\sigma_D = 277,6 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Zugbruchspannung im
Deckblech

σ_{11}^2	= 220 N/mm ²
E_{11}^2	= 152 kN/mm ²
σ_{11}^1	= 165 N/mm ²
E_{22}^2	= 130 kN/mm ²
$\sigma_{(45)}^2$	= 420 N/mm ²
$E_{(45)}^2$	= 181 kN/mm ²

Fig.11 Static tests of the components of the load transfer element

MBB

Fig.12 Test set-up

Fig.13 Results and evaluation of tests